

Evaluation of an Appropriate Parameter for Steric Effect**

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The observed pKa values of eight sets of substituted organic acids have been fitted to the equation, $pK_a = p_i^0 + \alpha_i f_j F_k + \beta_i r_j R_k + \delta f(\text{steric})$, where $f_j F_k$, $r_j R_k$ and $f(\text{steric})$ refer to field, resonance and steric factors respectively. The values of p_i^0 , α_i , β_i and δ are obtained by multiple regression analysis method. From the values of multiple correlation co-efficient and t-test, it has been concluded that steric density (SD) is also an appropriate parameter for steric effect.

SWAIN and Lupton¹ proposed two position independent parameters, F and R to explain the effect of the substituents attached to the benzene ring. Williams and Norrington² suggested positional weighting factors, f and r, for these parameters and showed the applicability in different equilibria by using equation 1.

$$pK_a = P_i^0 + \alpha_i f_j F_k + \beta_i r_j R_k \pm e_i \quad \dots (1)$$

However, it is noted that the calculated values for ortho-substituted compounds deviate markedly from the observed ones due to some perturbation. No steric term was incorporated in the above equation perhaps due to Charton's³ work that ortho substituents attached to sp² carbon exert only electronic effect. To explain the perturbation noted by Williams and Norrington, it was hoped that the incorporation of an appropriate steric term may explain the results better. With this background equation 2 has been written.

$$pK_a = P_i^0 + \alpha_i f_j F_k + \beta_i r_j R_k + \delta f(\text{steric}) \pm e_i \quad \dots (2)$$

In these equations, P_i^0 is the value of the intercept; F_k and R_k are the field and the resonance parameters respectively for different substituents; f_j and r_j are the positional weighting factors for different positions of the benzene nucleus; α_i and β_i represent the sensitivity of the reaction to the substituent dependent products $f_j F_k$ and $r_j R_k$ respectively for a given reaction series, δ is the sensitivity of the reaction to the appropriate steric function, $f(\text{steric})$. The different steric functions chosen for the present analysis are ΔV_w , $\Delta \log V_w$ and steric density (SD) where,

$$V_w = (V_w)_{\text{substituent}} - (V_w)_H = (V_w)_k - 3.45,$$

$$\log V_w = \log(V_w)_k - \log(V_w)_H = \log(V_w)_k - 0.538$$

$$SD = (M.W/V_w)_k - (M.W/V_w)_H = (M.W/V_w)_k - 0.29$$

M.W is the molecular weight and V_w is the van der Waal's volume⁴ for different substituents, k.

The following sets of data have been analysed in the present work.

Set 1 : pKa of 2-substituted phenoxyacetic acids⁵ (n=9). H 3.171, F 3.085, Cl 3.051, Br 3.123, I 3.173, CN 2.975, NO₂ 2.896, CH₃ 3.227, OCH₃ 3.231.

Set 2 : pKa of 2-substituted benzoic acids⁶ F 3.267, Cl 2.9215, Br 2.854, I 2.863, Me 3.9083, Et 3.793, OMe 4.094, Ph 3.46, H 4.203, NO₂ 2.173.

Set 3 : pKa of 2-substituted paraaminobenzoic acids⁷ H 4.67, F 4.13, Cl 3.88, Br 3.69, I 3.81, OH 3.52, NO₂ 2.78, NH₂ 5.81, OMe 5.04, OEt 5.09, OC₃H₇ 4.96, OC₄H₉ 5.25, CH₃ 4.83, OC₅H₁₁ 5.1.

Set 4 : pKa of substituted thiophene-2-carboxylic acids⁸ H 3.51, o-OMe 4.25, o-Me 3.9, o-SMe 3.86, o-Br 3.24, o-SOMe 2.92, o-SO₂Me 2.56, m-Br 3.15, m-NO₂ 2.8, p-OMe 3.78, p-Me 3.74, p-SMe 3.51, p-Br 3.27, p-SO₂Me 2.81, p-Cl 3.3; p-NO₂ 2.78, m-Me 3.58.

Set 5 : pKa of cinnamic acids⁵ H 4.438, o-Cl 4.234, o-NO₂ 4.151, o-OH 4.613, o-Me 4.5, o-OMe 4.46, m-Cl 4.293, m-NO₂ 4.12, m-OH 4.397, m-Me 4.42, m-OMe 4.376, p-Cl 4.413, p-NO₂ 4.046, p-Me 4.564, p-OMe 4.54.

Set 6 : pKa of phenylacetic acids⁵ H 4.312, o-Cl 4.068, o-Br 4.053, o-I 4.038, o-NO₂ 4.004, m-Cl 4.14, m-I 4.159, m-NO₂ 3.967, p-Et 4.373, p-C₂H₅(i) 4.391, p-Bu(t) 4.417, p-F 4.246, p-Cl 4.19, p-Br 4.188, p-I 4.178, p-NO₂ 3.851, p-Me 4.37, p-OMe 4.36.

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Set 7 : pKa of β -phenylpropionicacids^o *o*-Me 4.6675, *m*-Me 4.6778, *p*-Me 4.684, *o*-OMe 4.8041, *m*-OMe 4.6536, *p*-OMe 4.69, *o*-Cl 4.5768, *m*-Cl 4.585, *p*-Cl 4.6073, *o*-NO₂ 4.5045, *p*-NO₂ 4.4737, H 4.6596.

Set 8 : pKa of phenylpropionicacids in 35% dioxan¹⁰ H 3.24, *o*-Cl 3.08, *o*-NO₂ 2.83, *o*-OMe 3.37, *m*-Cl 3.00, *m*-NO₂ 2.73, *m*-OMe 3.21, *p* Cl 3.07, *p*-NO₂ 2.57, *p*-OMe 3.44.

Results and Discussion

The squared correlations (r^2) between different parameters and pKa have been calculated and given in Table 1. The values of P_j^2 , α_j , β_j , δ , multiple correlation co-efficient (R), standard errors (s) and F-test are evaluated by usual statistical methods and given in Table 2.

The results in Table 1 reveal that there is a greater degree of collinearity between the pKa and the field effect values compared to other effects.

A comparison of field and resonance effects among all sets indicate an order $3 > 2 > 4 > 8 > 6 > 5 > 1 > 7$ for field effect and $2 > 3 > 4 > 8 > 5 > 6 > 1 > 7$ for resonance effect. The order is same except a reversal between sets 5, 6 and 2, 3 is noted. The reversal in the sensitivity values between sets 2 and 3 is due to a substantial contribution of the resonating structures involving *p*-amino group. Obviously the demand on 'X' decreases

in paraaminobenzoicacids compared to 2-substituted benzoicacids. In the sets 5 and 6, presence of a double bond in set 5 increases the sensitivity to the resonance contribution of the substituent. Hence a reversal in the order between sets 5 and 6 is noted.

The sensitivity of the pKa values to resonance and steric effect for 2-substituted phenoxyaceticacids (set 1) and substituted beta-phenylpropionicacids (set 7) are almost equal. The sensitivity to resonance contribution is about 0.27 to 0.28. In view of the fact that no resonance interaction is possible with the substituents and reaction site, this value appears significant. The nature of the substituent makes the aryl group an

electron repelling (II) or an attracting one (III).

TABLE 1—SQUARED CORRELATIONS OF THE VARIABLES FOR DIFFERENT SETS

		$f_j F_k$	$r_j R_k$	f(steric)		
				V_w	$\log V_w$	SD
Set 1	pKa	0.65	0.487	0.014	0.004	0.061
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.076	0.074	0.17	0.365
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.065	0.013	0.0002
Set 2	pKa	0.761	0.153	0.004	0.054	0.379
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.003	0.042	0.0005	0.39
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.012	0.0003	0.03
Set 3	pKa	0.609	0.385	0.155	0.047	0.283
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.118	0.0002	0.023	0.365
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.148	0.206	0.026
Set 4	pKa	0.608	0.43	0.032	0.0007	0.006
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.144	0.119	0.064	0.069
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.255	0.108	0.041
Set 5	pKa	0.588	0.59	0.004	0.012	0.002
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.092	0.055	0.047	0.154
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.004	0.08	0.043
Set 6	pKa	0.837	0.305	0.223	0.228	0.173
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.105	0.244	0.252	0.152
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.019	0.019	0.002
Set 7	pKa	0.502	0.612	0.009	0.005	0.027
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.107	0.075	0.092	0.262
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.004	0.004	0.003
Set 8	pKa	0.633	0.763	0.01	0.01	0.00001
	$f_j F_k$	1.0	0.305	0.123	0.124	0.179
	$r_j R_k$		1.0	0.012	0.012	0.0002

TABLE 2—SUMMARY OF STATISTICAL DATA FOR REGRESSION ANALYSIS WITH EQUATION (2).

Set	f(Steric)	P_i^a	α_i	β_i	δ	R^a	F^b	$S_{\sigma_{\epsilon i}}^c$	S_{α}^c	S_{β}^c	S_{δ}^c	n^d	C.L. ^e %
1	ΔV_w	3.162	-0.177	-0.266	0.0042	0.964	21.8	0.038	0.032	0.08	0.0027	9	99
	$\Delta \log V_w$	3.153	-0.181	-0.28	0.092	0.962	20.66	0.039	0.034	0.079	0.064	9	99
	SD	3.171	-0.199	-0.284	0.017	0.968	24.8	0.036	0.036	0.072	0.009	9	99
	nil	3.181	-0.159	-0.31	—	0.946	—	0.043				9	
2	ΔV_w	3.96	-1.156	-1.375	-0.012	0.961	23.89	0.223	0.149	0.492	0.006	10	99
	$\Delta \log V_w$	4.067	-1.104	-1.465	-0.511	0.969	30.96	0.198	0.129	0.433	0.211	10	99
	SD	3.809	-0.891	-1.713	-0.097	0.957	21.83	0.232	0.199	0.528	0.06	10	99
	nil	3.748	-1.097	-1.486	—	0.938	—	0.257				10	
3	ΔV_w	4.73	-1.46	-1.023	0.0157	0.908	15.68	0.401	0.301	0.593	0.0075	14	99
	$\Delta \log V_w$	4.659	-1.497	-1.108	0.489	0.881	11.5	0.454	0.362	0.73	0.46	14	99
	SD	4.833	-1.192	-1.557	-0.072	0.872	10.54	0.47	0.432	0.634	0.113	14	99
	nil	4.792	-1.355	-1.532	—	0.866	—	0.457				14	
4	ΔV_w	3.676	-0.748	-0.895	0.0147	0.92	23.77	0.207	0.131	0.204	0.005	17	99
	$\Delta \log V_w$	3.655	-0.736	-0.808	0.412	0.931	28.01	0.193	0.121	0.178	0.128	17	99
	SD	3.671	-0.764	-0.725	0.202	0.936	30.54	0.186	0.118	0.167	0.058	17	99
	nil	3.739	-0.68	-0.659	—	0.872	—	0.249				17	
5	ΔV_w	4.418	-0.223	-0.467	0.001	0.952	35.39	0.058	0.038	0.078	0.003	15	99.9
	$\Delta \log V_w$	4.419	-0.229	-0.446	0.044	0.954	37.38	0.057	0.037	0.081	0.053	15	99.9
	SD	4.422	-0.235	-0.447	0.014	0.954	37.2	0.057	0.04	0.081	0.017	15	99.9
	nil	4.42	-0.219	-0.471	—	0.951	—	0.058				15	
6	ΔV_w	4.317	-0.289	-0.31	-0.001	0.955	47.85	0.054	0.034	0.091	0.003	18	99.9
	$\Delta \log V_w$	4.317	-0.289	-0.31	-0.02	0.954	47.8	0.054	0.035	0.091	0.054	18	99.9
	SD	4.316	-0.28	-0.319	-0.01	0.958	52.63	0.052	0.032	0.087	0.008	18	99.9
	nil	4.318	-0.295	-0.309	—	0.954	—	0.053				18	
7	ΔV_w	4.639	-0.107	-0.267	0.003	0.941	20.48	0.035	0.025	0.059	0.002	12	99
	$\Delta \log V_w$	4.639	-0.108	-0.267	0.061	0.939	19.84	0.036	0.025	0.06	0.037	12	99
	SD	4.643	-0.112	-0.274	0.015	0.93	16.98	0.038	0.03	0.064	0.013	12	99
	nil	4.643	-0.094	-0.285	—	0.917	—	0.039				12	
8	ΔV_w	3.231	-0.411	-0.652	0.012	0.976	40.1	0.074	0.083	0.146	0.005	10	99.9
	$\Delta \log V_w$	3.231	-0.411	-0.652	0.23	0.976	40.46	0.074	0.084	0.146	0.092	10	99.9
	SD	3.23	-0.418	-0.685	0.068	0.979	46.97	0.069	0.078	0.131	0.024	10	99.9
	nil	3.185	-0.308	-0.794	—	0.951	—	0.098				10	

a = Multiple correlation co-efficient ;
b = F-test for significance of regression ;
c = Standard errors of the estimate, α_i , β_i and δ ;
d = Number of points in the set ; and
e = Confidence level of regression.

This difference in behaviour is due to the resonance interaction of the substituent. Hence the sensitivity appears significant.

In all sets the value of multiple correlation coefficient increases with the introduction of a steric parameter. The confidence with which all the three parameters need to be used is also more than 99% (Table 2).

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